

PRACTICAL IDEOLOGICAL AND POLITICAL EDUCATION: AN INNOVATIVE DIRECTION OF MEDIA PRACTICAL TEACHING FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF GRAND IDEOLOGICAL AND POLITICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract

The practical teaching of media in colleges and universities faces ideological and political dilemmas such as insufficient awareness of the overall situation, weak systematic thinking, and low willingness of students to participate. The construction of Grand Ideological and Political Education provides ideas for solving these dilemmas. Through the four-dimensional integration of subjects, content, fields, and methods, a systematic education model is formed. Taking Practical Ideological and Political Education as its innovative direction, media practical teaching relies on the educational logic of penetration, collaboration, practice, and closed-loop. In line with the basic requirements of enhancing political stance, strengthening the teaching system, coordinating teaching strategies, and emphasizing historical thinking, it reconstructs the dual-core teaching objectives, updates teaching content, expands dual-field teaching scenarios, and reforms teaching methods. This realizes the coupling of technical operation and value internalization in media practical teaching, solves the problem of integrating ideological and political education, and cultivates compound media talents with both technical capabilities and ideological and political literacy.

Keywords: Practical Ideological and Political Education, Grand Ideological and Political Education, Media Practical Teaching, Teaching Innovation.

INTRODUCTION

With the continuous development of science and technology, the digital wave represented by smart phones and mobile Internet has swept the world, and “mediated existence” has become the normal life of digital citizens.

To adapt to this social situation, many colleges and universities have set up various media-related courses, with a particular preference for practical media courses such as creative photography, digital video shooting, film and television editing, image processing, advertising creativity, and short video operation.

The so-called media practical teaching refers to the teaching activities in which teachers guide students to use the theoretical knowledge they have learned in various practical activities to cultivate and exercise the comprehensive application of various knowledge and skills. Teachers present the theoretical knowledge of media to students according to their original occurrence, development, movement and change, so that students can acquire rich perceptual knowledge and direct participation experience through hearing, witnessing and hands-on (Liu Qian, 2011).

Practical teaching covers content related to multiple disciplines such as journalism, advertising, communication, film and television studies, and design, which is conducive to improving teaching effectiveness.

According to the enrollment situation of the public optional course “Film and Television Editing” at the University of Shanghai for Science and Technology, students majoring in science and engineering such as electrical engineering, automation, computer science, optoelectronic information, and energy and power also show high interest. However, beyond this high interest, the practical teaching of media is plagued by ideological and political problems such as insufficient awareness of the overall situation, weak systematic thinking, and low willingness of students to participate, resulting in limited improvement in teaching effectiveness.

The ongoing construction of Grand Ideological and Political Education provides a new opportunity and idea for enhancing the manifestation of Curriculum-based Ideological and Political Education in the practical teaching of media courses in colleges and universities, namely Practical Ideological and Political Education. Based on an analysis of the practical dilemmas in integrating Curriculum-based Ideological and Political Education into media practical teaching, this paper elaborates on the core connotation of the Grand Ideological and Political Education concept, and further explores strategies to solve the dilemma of integrating ideological and political education into media practical teaching from the perspective of Grand Ideological and Political Education, with Practical Ideological and Political Education as the innovative direction.

1. Practical Dilemmas in Integrating Curriculum-based Ideological and Political Education into Media Practical Teaching

The practical teaching of media in colleges and universities faces the dilemma that the integration of ideological and political education is not in-depth, solid, or flexible. These dilemmas directly lead to the disconnection between technical training and value guidance, i.e., the imbalance between technical attractiveness and the penetrating power of ideological and political education.

Specifically, there are problems such as insufficient awareness of the overall situation, weak systematic thinking, and low willingness to participate in the teaching process. These problems restrict the cultivation of compound media talents, making media practical teaching “focus on skills while neglecting literacy” and failing to achieve the fundamental goal of educating people and cultivating talents.

1.1 Insufficient Awareness of the Overall Situation

People often hold the view that practical teaching is simply to enable students to apply theories and technologies to practical training. Guided by this concept, practical teaching focuses on imparting “skills” (i.e., technical transmission) (Zhang Xiaofeng, 2021).

This leads to an obvious preference among teachers and students in the teaching process: they pay attention to industry needs and commercial interests that can increase the chance of

winning awards, while ignoring the major changes unseen in a century in the world and the overall strategy of the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation, thus resulting in insufficient awareness of the overall situation (Shi Shuchen, 2022). From the perspective of Grand Ideological and Political Education, the practical teaching of media courses should not cultivate “professionals without souls”, but rather nurture new-era socialist successors with a sense of family and country, responsibility, and commitment.

On the one hand, efforts should be made to cultivate talents of the times who can take on the responsibility of national rejuvenation, and improve students' comprehensive quality through the “five-in-one” education of morality, intelligence, physical education, aesthetics, and labor education to promote their all-round development (Zhang Xiaofeng, 2021); on the other hand, students should be guided to understand China and the world with an open attitude and a global perspective, and enhance their national identity and national self-confidence through comparisons between China and foreign countries (Shi Shuchen, 2022).

1.2 Weak Systematic Thinking

Systematic thinking refers to a thinking method that regards the object of cognition as a system and comprehensively understands, analyzes, and solves problems from the interconnections and interactions between the system and its elements, between elements, and between the system and the environment (Shi Shuchen, 2022).

Both in society and within colleges and universities, the stereotype that “liberal arts are useless” is prevalent. As a result, the implementation of media practical teaching tends to focus on organizing and participating in practical competitions, and competition-based teaching has almost become the only link between practical teaching and Curriculum-based Ideological and Political Education.

This leads to a prominent problem of weak systematic thinking in the teaching process: Curriculum-based Ideological and Political Education and practical teaching are mainly confined to in-class and on-campus settings, with insufficient interaction and linkage with other elements, not to mention breaking through the narrowness limited to the limited time and space of classrooms and campuses.

1.3 Low Willingness of Students to Participate

In the implementation of practical teaching, students passively accept the knowledge imparted by teachers. In addition, the overall shortage of experimental equipment and the low overall utilization rate of such equipment make it difficult to carry out diverse experimental teaching.

This leads to many students lacking interest and enthusiasm in ideological and political practice, having no initiative to explore professional knowledge independently, being insufficient in original ability and poor in hands-on skills, and failing to view the technical prospects and imagination of the contemporary world from the perspective of Grand Ideological and Political Education. The practical teaching of media courses must practice the student-centered educational concept, give play to students' subjectivity in learning, and stimulate their potential independent learning ability.

2. The Core Connotation of the Concept of Grand Ideological and Political Education

In January 2025, the CPC Central Committee and the State Council issued *the Outline for Building a Powerful Education Nation (2024-2035)*, which clearly proposed to create a number of “Grand Ideological and Political Courses” brands, strengthen the education on socialist core values, and promote the Grand Ideological and Political Education from the conceptual level to the practical level.

The so-called “Grand Ideological and Political Education” concept refers to the practice in which schools, in implementing the fundamental task of fostering virtue through education, make full use of and give play to the ideological and political education functions of various subjects, courses, and resources to form a coordinated education effect.

Formulations such as “all-round education by all staff in the whole process”, “Curriculum-based Ideological and Political Education”, “integrated ideological and political courses in primary, secondary and tertiary education”, and “Grand Ideological and Political Courses” have been gradually formed in the process of implementing the concept of the “Grand Ideological and Political Education” (Shi Shuchen, 2022).

It is not a simple expansion of ideological and political education, but a systematic education model formed based on the educational needs of the new era. It attaches importance to the intervention and guiding role of teaching, and shows an obvious interdisciplinary trend.

2.1 “Grand” in Subjects: From Ideological and Political Teachers Working Alone to All-staff Coordinated Education

Traditional ideological and political education mostly relies on ideological and political teachers working alone, while professional teachers often regard the integration of ideological and political elements as an additional task, leading to the disconnection between professional teaching and ideological and political education.

Grand Ideological and Political Education emphasizes that there are no boundaries in educational subjects. It incorporates professional teachers, administrative staff, industry mentors, student peers, and even social forces into the educational system to form a coordinated educational community.

This subject structure breaks the barrier that ideological and political teachers are not familiar with media and professional teachers are not familiar with ideological and political education, turning the integration of ideological and political elements from a passive requirement into an active participation.

The Opinions on Strengthening and Improving Ideological and Political Work in Colleges and Universities under the New Situation clearly proposes to “adhere to all-round education by all staff in the whole process”, taking “all staff” as the primary prerequisite for Grand Ideological and Political Education.

2.2 “Grand” in Content: From One-way Output of Ideological and Political Theories to Value Integration in All Courses

Traditional ideological and political education mainly focuses on theoretical teaching, with content centered on the basic principles of Marxism and the history of the Party, which is loosely connected with professional practice; while professional courses focus on knowledge and skills, ignoring value guidance. The “grandness” in the content of Grand Ideological and Political Education lies in breaking the boundary between ideological and political courses and professional courses, and organically embedding ideological and political elements into professional teaching content to realize that courses serve as carriers of ideological and political education.

Firstly, it involves the excavation of ideological and political connotations in the core of disciplines, such as the Marxist View of Journalism (authenticity, principle of party spirit) and media ethics (privacy protection, governance of false information) in media practice; secondly, it involves the value connection in technical practice, such as integrating copyright ethics into the teaching of AI-generated content and emphasizing data authenticity and people's livelihood care in data journalism practice; thirdly, it involves the ideological and political connection with social issues, such as transforming social issues such as rural revitalization and red culture inheritance into media practice tasks, enabling students to understand national strategies and social responsibilities in technical operations.

2.3 “Grand” in Fields: From Classroom-based Ideological and Political Education to All-scenario Education

The field of traditional ideological and political education is mostly limited to ideological and political classrooms, while Grand Ideological and Political Education emphasizes that there are no blind spots in educational fields. It extends ideological and political education to all scenarios such as classrooms, laboratories, industry frontlines, and community practice, realizing that practice is the process of ideological and political education. For media practical teaching, the expansion of fields includes three dimensions: firstly, the ideological and political transformation of laboratory scenarios, such as setting up simulated political news broadcasting in virtual studios and incorporating training on the responsibility of public opinion guidance; secondly, the ideological and political extension of industry scenarios, such as organizing students to participate in media practice in mainstream media or industry companies, so that they can understand the political attributes of media in real work scenarios; thirdly, the ideological and political implementation in community scenarios, such as guiding students to create short videos on promoting the elimination of the digital divide among the elderly and building community cultural IPs in communities, transforming media technology into the ability to serve society.

2.4 “Grand” in Methods: From Theoretical Teaching to All-method Penetration

Traditional ideological and political education mostly adopts the method of one-way indoctrination, which is difficult to adapt to the practice-oriented and technology-sensitive characteristics of media majors. The “grandness” in the methods of Grand Ideological and

Political Education lies in abandoning the didactic ideological and political education and adopting diversified methods such as experiential, practical, and technical methods, turning ideological and political education from passive acceptance to active internalization. Specific methods include: firstly, the project-driven method, such as media practice projects centered on real social issues (e.g., the rural revitalization short video program); secondly, the technology-empowered method, such as using big data to analyze the value orientation of students' works to achieve precise ideological and political guidance; thirdly, the reflective discussion method, such as organizing seminars on media ethics cases to conduct critical discussions on issues such as AI-generated false news and the tendency of prioritizing traffic.

The “grandness” of Grand Ideological and Political Education essentially lies in the reconstruction and expansion of the boundaries of ideological and political education, which is reflected in the grand integration of the four dimensions of subjects, content, fields, and methods. Its core goal is to turn ideological and political education from an additional question into a mandatory question, and from a solo dance into a group dance. Compared with traditional ideological and political education, the "all-staff, all-courses, all-scenarios, and all-methods" of Grand Ideological and Political Education in terms of subjects, content, fields, and methods place greater emphasis on integration, the overall situation, practicality, systematicness, coordination, and historicity. It is highly consistent with the disciplinary characteristics of media practical teaching, which focuses on technical carriers, practice orientation, and value shaping. We can take “Practical Ideological and Political Education” as a breakthrough point, embed ideological and political goals into the entire process of media practical teaching, and realize the in-depth coupling of technical operation and value internalization.

3. Practical Ideological and Political Education: The Grand Ideological and Political Innovation of Media Practical Teaching

The so-called Practical Ideological and Political Education is a whole-process ideological and political model driven by practical operation, which organically combines ideological and political education with practical teaching, and guides students to experience life, think and communicate, and realize sublimation in media practice scenarios, thereby improving their ideological and political quality and media practical ability. Practical Ideological and Political Education is not only the materialization of the Grand Ideological and Political Education concept in the process of media practical teaching, but also the innovative direction of media practical teaching under the guidance of the Grand Ideological and Political Education concept. Of course, we do not require covering all aspects, but rather doing what we can based on our capabilities.

3.1 Educational Logic of Practical Ideological and Political Education

The educational logic of Practical Ideological and Political Education is not linear indoctrination, but a four-dimensional transmission mechanism formed based on the cognitive laws of human beings and the disciplinary characteristics of media. Its core is to realize the transformation of ideological and political education from cognition to internalization and then to practice.

3.1.1 Penetration Logic: From External Requirements to Internal Integration

The core of Grand Ideological and Political Education is to reject labeled ideological and political education and emphasize the organic penetration of ideological and political elements into media practice. Therefore, the logical starting point of Practical Ideological and Political Education is to respect the laws of professional disciplines and transform ideological and political requirements into internal standards of professional practice. For example, authenticity in media practice is not only a core requirement of the Marxist View of Journalism, but also a basic principle of media professionalism. In data journalism teaching, teachers do not need to emphasize ideological and political education additionally; instead, through data verification training (e.g., identifying sources of false data), students can naturally understand the ideological and political connotation of authenticity in technical operations. This penetrating logic avoids the disconnection between ideological and political education and professional teaching, enabling students to comprehend ideological and political concepts while learning professional knowledge.

3.1.2 Coordination Logic: From a Single Subject to Systematic Linkage

The educational effect of Grand Ideological and Political Education depends on the coordination of various subjects and links. Therefore, the core logic of Practical Ideological and Political Education is to break down educational barriers and form a joint force. Specifically, the coordination logic includes two levels: firstly, curriculum coordination, for example, the digital video shooting course focuses on value expression in images (e.g., composition design for rural revitalization themes), and the short video operation course focuses on social responsibility in communication (e.g., avoiding vulgarization), forming a "curriculum chain = ideological and political chain"; secondly, field coordination, such as classroom learning (theory) - laboratory simulation (technology) - industry practice (application) - community service (implementation), realizing all-scenario ideological and political coverage.

3.1.3 Practice Logic: From Theoretical Cognition to Action Internalization

Grand Ideological and Political Education emphasizes that practice is the key to the internalization of ideological and political concepts. Therefore, Practical Ideological and Political Education should enable students to learn by doing and comprehend by learning. For media practical teaching, the practice logic is reflected in transforming ideological and political requirements into operable practical tasks, enabling students to internalize values while completing tasks. For example, in the advertising creativity course, traditional teaching focuses on creative conception, while under the perspective of Practical Ideological and Political Education, emphasis is placed on designing public service advertising creation tasks. Students need to design advertising schemes for the education of left-behind children. They not only need to master skills such as audience analysis, copywriting, and shooting and editing, but also need to understand the social significance of the left-behind children issue through research, and finally convey the values of caring for vulnerable groups in their works. This practice-driven logic turns ideological and political education from abstract theories into concrete

actions, deepening teachers' and students' understanding of Practical Ideological and Political Education.

3.1.4 Closed-loop Logic: From Goal Setting to Optimization and Iteration

The education of Practical Ideological and Political Education is a dynamically optimized closed-loop process, which is a cycle of goal-setting - implementation - evaluation - improvement. Specifically, the closed loop includes four links: firstly, the setting of ideological and political goals, for example, clearly defining the three-dimensional goals of value orientation, ethical compliance, and social responsibility in media practical courses; secondly, teaching implementation, which implements the goals through penetration, coordination, and practice methods; thirdly, ideological and political evaluation, which assesses the effectiveness through diversified evaluation; fourthly, improvement and optimization, which adjusts the teaching content according to the evaluation results, such as increasing certain types of ethical cases and strengthening the practice of panoramic shooting.

3.2 Basic Requirements of Practical Ideological and Political Education

From the perspective of Grand Ideological and Political Education, Practical Ideological and Political Education can strengthen students' practical ability, innovative spirit, and sense of social responsibility by enhancing political stance, strengthening the teaching system, coordinating teaching strategies, and emphasizing historical thinking, thereby promoting students to continuously improve their own quality in practice.

3.2.1 Enhancing Political Stance

The core of Practical Ideological and Political Education is to implement Xi Jinping Thought on Socialism with Chinese Characteristics for a New Era and practice socialist core values through concrete actions (Zhu Haibing & Tang Ying, 2021). Under the background of the construction of Grand Ideological and Political Education, it is necessary to broaden the perspective and not equate practical teaching with the skill training of media creation. It is necessary not only to cultivate students' ability to apply knowledge and practice, but also to develop their innovative spirit, sense of family and country, sense of social responsibility, humanistic literacy, and scientific literacy (Zhang Xiaofeng, 2021).

Students should be encouraged to take on the responsibility and mission of telling Chinese stories well and spreading Chinese voices well, and promote practical teaching to evolve into Practical Ideological and Political Education teaching. It is necessary to focus on society, take themes such as fighting the epidemic, poverty alleviation, rural revitalization, and building a modern socialist country in an all-round way, and organically integrate the acquisition of professional knowledge with the socialized development of individuals into practical teaching. In this way, we can adhere to the ideological, theoretical, political, and guiding nature of Grand Ideological and Political Education, focus on the fundamental task of fostering virtue through education, and guide students to firmly become socialist builders and successors with all-round development of morality, intelligence, physical education, aesthetics, and labor education (Shi Shuchen, 2022).

3.2.2 Strengthening the Teaching System

From the perspective of Grand Ideological and Political Education, the Practical Ideological and Political Education teaching of media courses should extensively mobilize all educational subjects inside and outside the classroom, on and off campus, and online and offline, and effectively integrate educational resources (Shi Shuchen, 2022). The content of media practical teaching can be divided into several progressive and integrated levels. Centering on the curriculum structure and content, practical teaching can be carried out around the knowledge absorption, technical training, and thinking guidance in the corresponding courses, so that students can master a solid theoretical foundation and practical ability. At the same time, it should not be limited to specific course content; through virtual or actual projects, students can be comprehensively trained in the quality and ability of the entire process from creative planning, team building, formal production to marketing and management analysis, and students should be encouraged to independently explore and discover the value and charm of Practical Ideological and Political Education. The teaching space should be expanded, with creation as the core, to cultivate creative awareness, stimulate creative potential, and develop innovative thinking in practical scenarios, and implement flexible evaluation standards (Tan Keng, 2010).

3.2.3 Coordinating Teaching Strategies

Centering on the orientation of Practical Ideological and Political Education, the integrated teaching of courses and competitions should be implemented. The focus should be shifted from professional segmentation to interdisciplinary integration, and course assignments should be combined with discipline competitions to guide students to transform the knowledge they have learned into specific works that can participate in competitions; students should be guided to write media review articles to improve their appreciation ability; students should be guided to actively carry out film and television cultural activities to improve the overall aesthetic education level of the school, and the focus should be shifted from adapting to services to supporting and leading; the dual-classroom strategy of online and offline should be implemented, giving full play to the auxiliary role of online classrooms, and completing the review and revision of students' works and cross-cultural communication in online cloud classrooms. On this basis, an ecological environment for Practical Ideological and Political Education that combines theory and practice, and links classrooms and resource libraries should be constructed. The individual potential of students should be accurately grasped, and appropriate practical projects should be selected for different students to improve their willingness to participate and promote the coordinated development of students' theoretical literacy and practical skills.

3.2.4 Emphasizing Historical Thinking

Historical thinking refers to a thinking method that learns from history to understand the present, looks forward to the future, and promotes development by using historical materialism to understand history, grasp reality, and look forward to the future. History is the best textbook. From the perspective of Grand Ideological and Political Education, it is necessary to

organically integrate vivid materials from China's long history, great practices, and real life into the Practical Ideological and Political Education teaching of media courses. In particular, the glorious journey and major achievements of the Communist Party of China in the past century are vivid teaching materials for Practical Ideological and Political Education. They can enhance the sense of the times, attractiveness, and appeal of Practical Ideological and Political Education in terms of theme style, character image, and ideological sublimation, enhance students' cultural confidence and national pride, and eliminate the consciousness of historical nihilism and indifference (Shi Shuchen, 2022).

3.3 Teaching Reform of Practical Ideological and Political Education

From the perspective of Grand Ideological and Political Education, media practical teaching can promote the specific improvement of the Practical Ideological and Political Education teaching model by reconstructing teaching objectives, updating teaching content, expanding teaching fields, and reforming teaching methods.

3.3.1 Reconstruction of Teaching Objectives

Break through the goal deviation of technology first and construct a dual-core goal system that emphasizes both technical literacy and value literacy, turning ideological and political goals from vague to specific. Firstly, the goal of technical literacy: it not only requires students to master media technologies (such as AI editing, data visualization, and virtual anchor operation), but also to understand the ethical requirements behind the technologies. Specifically, it includes technical compliance (such as copyright awareness of AI-generated content and the legality of data crawling), technical ethics (such as breaking the information cocoon of algorithm recommendation and controlling the value orientation of virtual anchors), and technical application (such as using VR technology to spread red culture).

Secondly, the goal of technical value: combined with the disciplinary characteristics of media, the value literacy is refined into specific assessable goals. For example, the cognitive goal is to understand the Marxist View of Journalism (authenticity, principle of party spirit) and the responsibility of media in guiding public opinion; the ethical judgment goal is to be able to handle ethical dilemmas in media practice (such as privacy protection, false information, and the balance between traffic and authenticity); the social responsibility goal is to be able to use media technology to serve society (such as rural revitalization, anti-fraud publicity, and cultural inheritance). Each technical goal must correspond to a value goal, forming an ideological and political logic in which technical operations serve the realization of values.

3.3.2 Update of Teaching Content

Realize the organic update of content through dual-layer excavation, and construct a three-dimensional integration system of professional knowledge - ideological and political elements - social issues, breaking the dilemma of labeling ideological and political elements and making ideological and political elements an inherent part of teaching.

The first layer is to excavate the ideological and political core of professional knowledge and construct a knowledge - ideological and political mapping relationship. Systematically sort out

the ideological and political integration points in various fields of media practice, and form a mapping table of professional knowledge - ideological and political elements to provide teachers with a clear integration path.

Table 1: Mapping Table of Professional Knowledge and Ideological and Political Elements

Professional Knowledge Field	Core Ideological and Political Elements	Example of Integration Path
News Authenticity	Marxist View of Journalism, Integrity Ethics	Incorporate data verification training in data journalism practice, and compare the communication effects of real and false data
AI-generated Content	Copyright Ethics, Governance of False Information	Introduce cases of copyright infringement in AI-generated news in teaching, and guide students to mark the sources of AI-generated content
Short Video Operation	Social Responsibility, Dissemination of Socialist Core Values	Require students to design short videos on social issues such as anti-fraud publicity and the digital divide among the elderly
Virtual Studio Broadcasting	Responsibility of Public Opinion Guidance, Political Cognition	Simulate the reporting of people's livelihood issues during the Two Sessions, and train students to accurately interpret policy expressions

The second layer is to develop an ideological and political case database to provide integration demonstration and construction. Collect typical cases of technology - ideological and political integration to provide reference for teachers.

The case database should include five parts: case background, technical key points, ideological and political integration path, students' works, and evaluation standards. The following is an example of the case of AI-generated false news identification.

Table 2: Case of AI-generated False News Identification

Case of AI-generated False News Identification	Case of AI-generated False News Identification
Background	AI-generated false disaster news appeared on a certain platform, causing panic
Technical Key Points	AI text analysis technology (identifying characteristics of false information), data source tracing technology
Ideological and Political Integration Path	Understand the social harm of false news and the responsibility of media in refuting rumors
Student Task	Use AI technology to identify false news and produce short videos on rumor identification guidelines
Evaluation Standard	Technical accuracy (80%) + Social value (20%)

3.3.3 Expansion of Teaching Fields

To break the scenario limitation that the integration of ideological and political education in media practical teaching is confined to classrooms, it is necessary to take "practice as ideological and political education" as the core orientation and construct an all-scenario education system in which literacy is cultivated in real scenarios and value practice runs through the whole process.

On the one hand, it is necessary to fully activate the existing on-campus media practice resources, rely on the professional photography studios, virtual studios and other hardware facilities of the university-level integrated media center, and deeply embed ideological and political goals into scenario-based practice. When carrying out red-themed image creation tasks in the photography studio, guide students to convey the revolutionary spirit and contemporary connotation through light and shadow composition and character modeling; when simulating political news broadcasting and people's livelihood issue interviews in the virtual studio, require students to accurately grasp the scale of public opinion guidance in camera scheduling and wording expression, and strengthen the sense of responsibility of media in serving people's livelihood, so that the on-campus scenario becomes a basic training position for ideological and political practice.

On the other hand, it is necessary to deepen school-enterprise cooperation with local leading media companies, establish co-construction bases for Practical Ideological and Political Education, and regularly select students to participate in the operation of real media projects. For example, joining the public welfare audio-visual creation team of media companies, and practicing the media ethics of "spreading positive energy" in program design and delivery execution, so that the real industry scenario becomes a practical training platform for tempering ideological and political literacy. Through the linkage between on-campus scenario foundation-laying and industry scenario quality improvement, ideological and political education is ensured to run through the whole process of practice, avoiding the formalization of the integration of ideological and political elements.

3.3.4 Reform of Teaching Methods

Abandon the traditional method of one-way indoctrination, and adopt diversified methods such as technical, practical, and reflective methods, turning the integration of ideological and political education from passive acceptance to active internalization, and constructing a diversified teaching method combining technology empowerment and practice drive. Firstly, project-driven immersive ideological and political practice: carry out project-based learning centered on real social issues, allowing students to complete the whole process of practice from topic demonstration - technical creation - result dissemination - reflective summary in groups, and internalize ideological and political literacy in the project.

Table 3: Three Elements of Project Design

Three Elements of Project Design	
Social Value Orientation	Projects must be connected to national strategies or social needs (e.g., rural revitalization, red culture inheritance)
Integration of Technology and Ideological and Political Education	Project tasks must include dual requirements of technical operation and value realization. For example, the rural revitalization short video project requires mastering UAV shooting + AI editing technology while conveying the concept of common prosperity;
Reflective Summary Link	After the project is completed, students are required to submit an ideological and political reflection report, analyzing how technology serves the realization of values, and the dilemmas encountered in practice and their solutions.

Secondly, the interdisciplinary collaborative method for deepening ideological and political education: cooperate with disciplines such as ideological and political courses and sociology to carry out interdisciplinary media practice, and deepen ideological and political cognition from multiple dimensions. For example, in the rural education data journalism project, sociology courses can teach rural research methods, ideological and political courses can focus on the national strategy of educational equity, and media courses can guide data visualization and news writing.

This interdisciplinary method breaks the limitations of a single discipline and helps students understand the connotation of ideological and political education from the technical, theoretical, and social dimensions. Practical Ideological and Political Education is not merely a simple extension of Ideological and Political Education in Courses.

Instead, guided by the concept of holistic Ideological and Political Education and with practical tasks as the core carrier, it transforms ideological and political requirements—such as the Marxist view of journalism, media ethics, and social responsibility—into operable, experiential, and reflective media practice activities.

This enables students to learn by doing and cultivate through insight, addressing the dilemma of insufficient, superficial, and rigid integration of ideological and political elements. It organically embeds ideological and political requirements into professional practice scenarios, allowing teachers and students to naturally internalize values while solving real-world problems, thereby truly realizing the coordinated development of knowledge, abilities, and values.

CONCLUSION

From the perspective of Grand Ideological and Political Education, the value of Practical Ideological and Political Education lies in breaking through the dual limitations of the empty operation of traditional ideological and political theories and the single track of technical teaching in professional courses, and transforming ideological and political requirements into operable media practice tasks.

This model of "learning by doing and cultivating through comprehension" not only enables students to deepen their understanding of the attributes of media in technical operations, but also awakens their sense of responsibility to serve national strategies and respond to people's livelihood needs through the involvement of real social issues, providing a practical solution to the dilemma of integrating ideological and political education into media practical teaching. Practical Ideological and Political Education is by no means a simple adjustment of a single teaching method, but a systematic reconstruction of the media talent training system.

It requires the innovation of teaching objectives, teaching content, teaching fields, and teaching methods under the guidance of the Grand Ideological and Political Education concept. This reconstruction not only conforms to the strategic requirement of "creating Grand Ideological and Political Course brands" in the *Outline for Building a Powerful Education Nation*, but also meets the demand of the media industry for compound talents with "excellent technology and

firm values”. The deepening of Practical Ideological and Political Education in media practice needs to continue to explore in the balance between technology empowerment and value adherence.

On the one hand, new technologies such as generative AI can be used to develop more immersive ideological and political practice scenarios (e.g., digital twin spaces for red media); on the other hand, a long-term evaluation mechanism needs to be established to further verify the long-term shaping effect of Practical Ideological and Political Education on the judgment and decision-making ability of media talents through the tracking of graduates' career development. Only in this way can a solid talent foundation be laid for the high-quality development of the media industry.

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